

pH-Metric Studies on the Interaction of Magnesium, Strontium, and Beryllium with Casein and α -Casein

S. K. Agarwal and Wahid U. Malik

pH-metric method has been employed to study the binding of magnesium, strontium, and beryllium to casein and α -casein. Results indicate that the binding of beryllium takes place through the carboxyl groups of α -casein only, whereas with casein, groups other than carboxyl are also involved. Magnesium and strontium combine through the imidazole and amino groups beside the carboxyl groups of both α -casein and casein. The order of binding for casein and α -casein is quite different: being $\text{Sr}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Be}^{2+}$ in the case of casein and $\text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Sr}^{2+} > \text{Be}^{2+}$ for α -casein.

pH measurement has been one of the earliest technique for the study of metallo-protein systems. It was used for the hydrogen-ion equilibria of proteins by a number of eminent workers, notably Cannan¹, Steinhardt², and Tanford³. Interaction of metal ions and also their hydrous oxide sols with proteins has recently been studied by Malik and co-workers⁴⁻⁵. They showed that the metal ions from the solutions as well as from their corresponding sols combined with the available sites of the protein under suitable pH conditions. Most of the work, however, deals with gelatin and very little has been done with respect to other proteins. In this communication results on the interaction of magnesium, strontium, and beryllium with casein and α -casein are reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

The whole casein used was a pure E. Merck product. α -Casein was prepared by using its differential solubility in 50% aqueous ethanol⁶ with change in pH and temperature.

Stock solutions of casein and α -casein were prepared by dissolving the air-dried protein in a minimum amount of *N*/10-KOH solution. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 12.0. The concentration of the stock solution was further checked by drying an aliquot to a constant weight at 105° and then correcting for potassium. This method provided the same value for protein concentration as was calculated on the basis of anhydrous weight of the protein used.

Magnesium chloride and strontium nitrate were A. R. products and beryllium nitrate was an E. Merck product. These were dissolved in double distilled water (all-glass appara-

1. Cannan *et al.*, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1941, **41**, 243.
2. Steinhardt and Zaiser, "Advances in Protein Chemistry", 1955, **10**, 151.
3. Tanford, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 441; 1957, **79**, 5340; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 5340.
4. Malik and Salahuddin, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1963, **5**, 68, 147; *this Journal*, 1964, **41**, 365, 362.
5. Raza *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1963, **40**, 1033.
6. "The Proteins", edited by H. Neurath and K. Bailey, Vol. II, Part A, p. 309.

tus) and their strength determined gravimetrically. An $M/50$ solution was then made by subsequent dilution and the pH maintained at 2.00 by addition of the requisite amount of $N/10$ -HCl solution.

HCl and KOH solutions were prepared and their pH s adjusted to 2.00 and 12.00, respectively. pH measurements were made with a Cambridge bench type pH -meter with the glass electrode at $30^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$. The special, blue-glass, high-alkali electrode was used for the more alkaline solutions.

Procedure.—Varying volumes, viz., 1,2,4,6,8,10,14,16 ml of the metal salt solution ($M/50$, pH 2.0) were taken in different Pyrex tubes. Two such sets were arranged. In one set a constant volume (4 ml) of the protein solution was added, whereas in the other set 4.0 ml of KOH solution of the same pH as that of the protein (12.00) was added; the total volume was then made to 20 ml by adding the requisite amount of water. The pH of these solutions was measured immediately and after 24 hr. The pH remained the same in both the cases.

TABLE I

Conc. of casein soln. = 2.0% (pH 12.00). pH of the HCl soln. = 2.0. pH of the KOH soln. = 12.0.

HCl added.	Casein			α -Casein		
	pH_1 .	pH_2 .	ΔpH .	pH_1 .	pH_2 .	ΔpH .
1 ml	10.44	10.70	0.26	10.60	11.10	0.50
2	7.34	10.56	3.22	8.64	11.08	2.44
4	3.08	9.34	6.26	3.24	10.50	7.26
6	2.66	7.74	5.08	2.80	9.72	6.92
8	2.46	6.55	4.09	2.60	8.04	5.44
10	2.36	4.00	1.64	2.50	5.80	3.30
12	2.24	3.10	0.86	2.42	4.14	1.72
14	2.16	2.80	0.64	2.38	3.40	1.02
16	2.08	2.56	0.48	2.24	3.00	0.76

The interaction of metal ions can take place either by competing with hydrogen ions or the hydroxyl ions, depending on the pH of the metal-protein system. If (H_1) and (H_2) represent the concentration of free hydrogen ions in KOH and anionic protein interaction with metal ions, then ΔpH (the difference between the two) indicates the extent of binding; the greater the ΔpH , the greater is the binding of the metal with the protein. The results are summarised in Tables I and II.

DISCUSSION

It is evident from Fig. 1 and 2 that the titration curves of magnesium, strontium, and beryllium for casein and α -casein, respectively, lie above the corresponding ones for the metal ions and the alkali. Since casein does not show any detectable ion binding with the

chloride⁷, the only explanation which may be offered for the variations in pH is the possible chemical combination of metal ions with the protein.

TABLE II

Conc. of salt soln. = $M/50$ (pH 2.0). Conc. of casein soln. same as in Table I.

Electrolyte added.	Casein			κ -Casein		
	pH_1 .	pH_2 .	ΔpH .	pH_1 .	pH_2 .	ΔpH .
A. $MgCl_2$ soln.						
16 ml	2.24	3.00	0.76	2.18	2.70	0.52
14	2.32	3.56	1.24	2.22	3.06	0.84
12	2.40	4.34	1.94	2.36	3.70	1.34
10	2.50	5.46	2.96	2.36	4.58	2.20
8	2.62	6.10	3.48	2.58	5.58	3.00
6	2.84	6.80	5.96	2.70	6.44	3.74
4	3.32	10.28	6.96	3.10	8.90	5.80
2	8.26	10.62	2.36	8.20	10.44	2.24
1	10.58	11.00	0.42	10.36	10.76	0.46
B. $Sr(NO_3)_2$ soln.						
16	2.20	2.84	0.64	2.20	2.80	0.60
14	2.24	3.24	1.00	2.28	3.20	0.92
12	2.36	4.00	1.64	2.42	4.00	1.58
10	2.46	5.16	2.70	2.62	5.60	2.98
8	2.56	5.86	3.30	2.82	7.10	4.28
6	2.74	7.02	4.28	3.80	10.14	6.34
4	6.26	9.30	6.04	10.80	10.80	..
2	8.20	10.72	2.52	11.20	11.20	..
1	10.52	10.94	0.42	11.30	11.30	..
C. $Be(NO_3)_2$ soln.						
16	2.12	2.58	0.46	2.44	3.30	0.86
14	2.20	2.74	0.54	2.50	3.80	1.30
12	2.24	3.00	0.76	2.64	4.06	1.42
10	2.36	3.54	1.18	2.90	4.40	1.50
8	2.54	3.90	1.36	3.40	4.74	1.34
6	2.68	4.40	1.78	4.34	5.48	1.06
4	3.00	5.02	2.02	5.08	6.80	1.72
2	4.60	8.20	3.60	10.70	10.90	0.10
1	5.82	10.60	4.78	11.20	11.20	..

In the lower pH range of 3.0 to 5.0, largest binding is observed for beryllium ions, which goes to show that this metal combines with casein mostly through its carboxyl groups (more so in the case of κ -casein). On the other hand, magnesium and strontium show the tendency to combine with protein even in the higher pH range where the imidazole, amino-acid, and phenolic (from the tyrosine residue of the protein) offer sites for combination.

7. Carr, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1953, **46**, 417.

8. Smythe and Schmidt, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, **88**, 241.

The order of combining tendencies for different metal ions, obtained on the basis of the above studies, is strontium > magnesium > beryllium for casein, and magnesium > strontium > beryllium in the case of α -casein.

FIG. 1

a_1, a_2, a_3 : electrolyte + casein.
 b_1, b_2, b_3 : electrolyte + KOH.

FIG. 2

a_1, a_2, a_3 : electrolyte + α -casein.
 b_1, b_2, b_3 : electrolyte + KOH.

Quantitative studies with special reference to the difference in behaviour of casein and α -casein towards magnesium are in progress.

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